

Experimental Covariances between Integral Critical Experiments: The Case Study of TEX-Chlorine and TEX-HEU

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ABSTRACT

Recent developments in nuclear data validation highlighted the deficiency in experimental covariances between integral benchmark evaluations. These benchmark evaluations, specifically critical experiments, rely heavily on communal components, such as fuel and structures, due to accessibility, budgets, and ease of benchmarking. There are obvious correlations between experiments that go beyond the isotopic makeup of the components that probe the nuclear data. For example, decades of experiments performed at TA-18 or NCERC rely on the same machinery and fuel. These correlations impact nuclear data adjustments and may impact benchmark selection via current similarity index methods by affecting χ^2 metrics. Covariance information has been derived for two benchmark evaluations with similar experimental structures and compared directly to produce the first interbenchmark correlations. These highly-correlated experiments prove this technique is viable in the current uncertainty quantification paradigm of the International Criticality Benchmark Evaluation Project and highlight the importance of determining experimental covariances. After quantifying the covariance between the TEX-Chlorine and TEX-HEU experiments, the χ^2 per degree of freedom decreased from 3.201 to 2.126. By omitting the covariances between the two experiments, an overly penalizing validation of the nuclear data would have occurred, i.e. an overestimation of the χ^2 .

Keywords: Nuclear Data, Covariance, Integral Benchmark, Chlorine, Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear data covariances have been a hot topic in the nuclear data community for a number of years, particularly since the transition from ENDF/B-VI.8 to ENDF/B-VII.0 for the US library [1]. While they existed abundantly in ENDF/B-VI.8, increased rigor led to their purge in ENDF/B-VII.0. Nuclear data covariances have been a major part of the upgrade between nuclear data libraries with new, high-quality covariance data in each new version of ENDF. Nuclear data covariances have an integral part in uncertainty quantification and validation studies. Similarity metrics such as c_k [2] or q_c [3] also utilize nuclear data covariances as an integral part of determining similarity between application cases.

What if, however, another important source of covariance is missing in validation studies? What if experimental benchmarks in the validation suite have a known but unquantified correlation between each other? Or of particular concern, what if the operation or application that is being validated is correlated to the experiments that make up the validation suite? This may have happened in Rocky Flats in the 1960s, 70s, and 80s or Y-12 in the 1940s and 50s. It is apparent that the covariance term becomes a broader endeavor.

Covariances between experimental benchmarks affects validation metrics like χ^2 . Furthermore, they impact upper subcritical limits (USLs) for criticality safety and perform nuclear data adjustment [4]. Inclusion of these covariances to the total covariance has shown to have an appreciable impact on the total χ^2 [5].

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Experimental covariances between benchmark evaluations may exist, where similar components, fuel, or facilities are re-used. These covariances are regularly ignored. However, these covariances can be extracted using the same information that is already required per the uncertainty guide for the ICSBEP [6,7]. The methodology for extracting these experimental covariances has already been presented [5] but is summarized, updated, and expanded upon in this article. The technique is broadened - for the first time- to a second benchmark evaluation to determine the covariances between two criticality benchmarks performed years apart but at the same facility and with the same fuel: TEX-HEU and TEX-Chlorine.

2. THEORY

Uncertainty quantification techniques for ICSBEP evaluations utilize two methods: perturbative sensitivity analysis and adjoint-based sensitivity analysis [8]. The focus of the previous work primarily focused on perturbative - or finite difference - sensitivity analysis, which is generally dictated by:

$$\delta k_{eff} = \sigma \frac{\Delta k_{eff}}{p} = \sigma S, \quad (1)$$

where δk_{eff} is the uncertainty in k_{eff} , σ is the associated standard deviation of some physical parameter, Δk_{eff} is the response in k_{eff} due to some perturbation (p) in the parameter. The sensitivity coefficient (S) is defined as the ratio of δk_{eff} to p . Adjoint-based uncertainty quantification follows a similar approach, but the sensitivity coefficient is determined through the adjoint-based sensitivity analysis performed by Monte Carlo functions such as the KSEN card in MCNP [9].

It is possible to expand this analysis into multi-dimensional space such that we observe correlations between two k_{eff} values due to shared parameter uncertainties. To do this, we define the number of integral parameters (I) and the number of assessed parameters (J). For the benchmarks assessed here, there are eight total cases: three for TEX-Chlorine [10] and five for TEX-HEU [11]. Each benchmark has many uncertain parameters (e.g., HEU diameter or polyethylene moderator mass) of which some may be shared between benchmarks (e.g., HEU diameter).

For each parameter j there exists an $I \times J$ diagonal matrix \mathbf{S}_j of sensitivity coefficients for each of the integral parameters:

$$\mathbf{S}_j = \begin{pmatrix} S_{1j} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & S_{Ij} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where no experimental covariance exists and whose size is dictated by the number of cases (i). Covariance information is introduced via an uncertainty matrix that is formed such as:

$$\mathbf{M}_j = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{i,j} \cdot \sigma_{i,j} & \cdots & \sigma_{i,j} \cdot \sigma_{i',j} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{i',j} \cdot \sigma_{i,j} & \cdots & \sigma_{i',j} \cdot \sigma_{i',j} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where if no correlation exists, the matrix reduces to the variance. The size of the uncertainty matrix is dictated by the number of cases and is formed as a compression of the individual part uncertainties. The covariance can then be determined through the sandwich rule [6] expressed as

$$\Sigma_{\text{model}} = \sum_j S_j^T M_j S_j. \quad (4)$$

Similarly, one can calculate the χ^2 metric using the covariances and the bias between the vectors of experimental (**E**) and computed (**C**) benchmark results. The total covariance between the integral parameters is the sum of sources from the experimental measurements, from the model of the benchmark, and from nuclear data, $\Sigma_{\text{total}} = \Sigma_{\text{model}} + \Sigma_{\text{Experimental}} + \Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$. The formulation for the χ^2 metric goes as

$$\chi^2 = (\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{E})^{-1} \Sigma_{\text{total}} (\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{E}). \quad (5)$$

The χ^2 metric is often reported as χ^2/ν , or chi-squared per degree of freedom, where ν is defined as the sample size minus one, or $\nu = I - 1$.

One may be able to recognize that expanding to multiple benchmarks simply involves the expansion of the overall case set to include the benchmark cases involved in two or more benchmark evaluations. In fact, this is simply just the addition of more cases into the covariance calculations presented in the head of this section. That is, one can expand the cases (i) to the total number of cumulative cases present. Novel to this work, covariances between benchmarks are investigated. A case study calculates the covariances between two similar benchmarks and quantifies its impact on χ^2 . For TEX-HEU and TEX-Chlorine, $i = 8$ and one would then expect an 8×8 covariance. Further, one can determine the correlation matrix from the covariance matrix, and also extract a cumulative χ^2 .

3. COVARIANCES

Covariance information for the TEX-HEU benchmark evaluation has already been presented in [6] and is summarized in Section 3.1. The TEX-Chlorine covariance data are presented here for the first time. Additionally, the covariance between the two benchmarks evaluations are presented here.

3.1. TEX-HEU

The TEX-HEU benchmark is a set of experiments designed by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL). Five configurations were evaluated spanning the entire median fission neutron energy regime, from thermal to fast. These evaluations serve as a baseline for the follow-on experiments that include TEX-Chlorine, TEX-Hafnium [12], Low-Temperature TEX [13], and TEX-Lithium [14].

The model covariances Σ_{Model} are the covariances associated with the model of the benchmark in a Monte Carlo code. A single independent measurement determines the integral parameter and therefore two integral parameters are considered to have no ‘experimental’ covariance. Instead, the uncertainty in the experiment (and therefore correlations between experiments) is assigned to how well the model reproduces the physical experiment, whose components themselves have uncertainty. Here, Σ_{Model} is directly derived using the uncertainty quantification in the benchmark evaluation from no additional information [6]. The model covariance for the TEX-HEU benchmark evaluation (in pcm²) is:

$$\Sigma_{\text{Model}} = \begin{pmatrix} 18233.6 & 4872.7 & 4479.3 & 5717.5 & 2551.6 \\ 4872.7 & 15299.3 & 3337.6 & 2899.0 & 1815.4 \\ 4479.3 & 3337.6 & 17051.2 & 3587.2 & 1661.9 \\ 5717.5 & 2899.0 & 3587.2 & 22459.5 & 2213.2 \\ 2551.6 & 1815.4 & 1661.9 & 2213.2 & 14391.2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

The experimental covariance, $\Sigma_{\text{Experimental}}$, is just the variance of the experimental measurements. These are derived from the uncertainty in the reactor period measurements. $\Sigma_{\text{Experimental}}$ for TEX-HEU is:

$$\Sigma_{\text{Experimental}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 9 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 16 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 16 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

The covariances from nuclear data $\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$ were determined using multigroup sensitivity coefficients calculated by KSEN in MCNP6.3 in the SCALE 44-group structure. The ENDF/B-VIII.0 covariances were processed into the same energy group structure. Applying Equation 4 gives $\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$ for TEX-HEU :

$$\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}} = \begin{pmatrix} 116605.3 & 90728.8 & 60581.3 & 35640.5 & 11098.1 \\ 90728.8 & 97602.0 & 70435.9 & 47002.9 & 17799.4 \\ 60581.3 & 70425.9 & 68247.2 & 53691.7 & 30480.7 \\ 35640.6 & 47002.9 & 53961.7 & 62996.3 & 53659.8 \\ 11098.1 & 17799.4 & 30480.7 & 53659.8 & 138183.8 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The total covariance, Σ_{total} , for the TEX-HEU benchmark is the sum of the individual components. Using Σ_{total} , the χ^2/ν was found to be 1.377. Removing only $\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$ from Σ_{total} gives $\chi^2/\nu=12.470$. Removing only Σ_{Model} gives $\chi^2/\nu=1.689$, which shows an overestimating without the inclusion of model covariance data. The covariance data of the $^{235}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ cross section were seen to have an important effect on χ^2/ν . Removal of this specific cross section resulted in $\chi^2/\nu=1.829$. With the inclusion of the $^{235}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ covariance data and ignoring the experimental covariance data the resulting

3.2. TEX-Chlorine

The TEX-Chlorine benchmark isolated the change in bias from TEX-HEU due to isotopes and/or reaction channels of Cl. Specifically, the experiment targeted the Cl neutron capture channel. The benchmark evaluation consisted of three configurations, or $I = 3$. The Σ_{Model} is directly derived from the benchmark evaluation [10] uncertainty quantification. The assessed model covariance was determined to be:

$$\Sigma_{\text{Model}} = \begin{pmatrix} 6279.0 & 7489.2 & 2538.7 \\ 7489.2 & 14760.7 & 5575.8 \\ 2538.7 & 5575.8 & 4883.6 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

$\Sigma_{\text{Experimental}}$ was taken as the experimental uncertainties which share no correlation:

$$\Sigma_{\text{Experimental}} = \begin{pmatrix} 169 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 169 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 169 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

$\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$ was calculated in the same manner as TEX-HEU:

$$\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}} = \begin{pmatrix} 41991.2 & 73514.3 & 50275.0 \\ 73514.3 & 137514.6 & 54470.9 \\ 50275.0 & 54470.9 & 174222.0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Σ_{total} for the TEX-Chlorine benchmark produced $\chi^2/\nu=6.078$, showing a significant increase from TEX-HEU. Further investigation is required, but preliminary thinking attributes this increased bias to the Cl nuclear data. When $\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$ is removed from the calculation, χ^2/ν was found to be 164.570. The large χ^2/ν value is the direct result of the large the uncertainties in the evaluated ^{35}Cl neutron capture cross sections. Again, the major contributor to that drop was the uncertainty in the $^{235}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ cross section.

Removal of this specific cross section resulted in $\chi^2/\nu=7.517$. Other large contributors to the nuclear data uncertainty are the ^{27}Al elastic and inelastic scattering cross sections and the ^{235}U elastic scattering cross section. If Σ_{Model} is removed from Σ_{total} , the resulting $\chi^2/\nu=32.795$, which shows a significant overestimation when the experimental covariances are ignored. It should be noted that no Cl covariance exists for ENDF/B-VIII.0. Recent evaluations provide a novel covariance, but it is not included as there are known formatting issues with the covariance data¹. Inclusion of this covariance will be studied later.

3.3. Interbenchmark Covariances

The two benchmarks can then be compared directly to each other. To accomplish this the case set was increased to include all eight configurations. That is, Σ_{Model} was expanded to be an 8x8 matrix which encompasses the shared uncertainties for all experiments.

Σ_{Model} was directly derived from the uncertainty quantification in both benchmark evaluations which use a significant number of similar parts. The assessed model covariance was determined to be:

$$\Sigma_{\text{Model}} = \begin{pmatrix} 6279.0 & 7489.2 & 2538.7 & -217.0 & -279.4 & -423.5 & -637.1 & -3065.6 \\ 7489.2 & 14760.7 & 5575.8 & -288.0 & -347.1 & -556.4 & -952.8 & -5792.0 \\ 2538.7 & 5575.8 & 4883.6 & 129.3 & 313.1 & -25.2 & -52.2 & -584.6 \\ -217.0 & -288.0 & 129.3 & 18233.6 & 4872.7 & 4479.3 & 5717.5 & 2551.6 \\ -279.4 & -347.1 & 313.1 & 4872.7 & 15299.3 & 3337.6 & 2899.1 & 1815.4 \\ -423.5 & -556.4 & -25.2 & 4479.3 & 3337.6 & 17051.2 & 3587.2 & 1661.9 \\ -637.1 & -952.8 & -52.2 & 5717.5 & 2899.1 & 3587.2 & 22459.5 & 2213.2 \\ -3065.6 & -5792.0 & -584.6 & 2551.6 & 1815.4 & 1661.9 & 2213.2 & 14391.2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

The first three columns represent the TEX-Chlorine configurations, and the last five columns represent the TEX-HEU configurations. The two benchmarks are inversely correlated as the sensitivity coefficients for the largest uncertainties were found to be inversely correlated. The correlation matrix for the model is shown in Figure 1.

¹ Via private communications with Marco Pigni (ORNL).

Figure 1: Correlation matrix for the TEX-Chlorine (cases 1-3) and the TEX-HEU (cases 4-8) cases using the model covariances, Σ_{Model} .

$\Sigma_{\text{Experimental}}$ is the concatenation of the two experimental covariances provided above (see Sections 3.1 and 3.2). $\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$ was also evaluated in the same way as above, but together in one large sandwich rule calculated to preserve nuclear data covariances between TEX-HEU and TEX-Cl. In the interest of space, neither covariance matrix will be explicitly presented here. Instead, Figure 2 shows the correlation matrix including all three covariance contribution matrices. It is apparent that the cases 7 and 8 (cases 4 and 5 in TEX-HEU) are the most correlated to the TEX-Chlorine cases 1 and 2. These cases are the most thermal configurations of each benchmark evaluation, which utilizes the most polyethylene moderator material. In general, the TEX-Chlorine configurations trend faster as the case number rises and the TEX-HEU configurations trend more thermal as the case number rises.

Figure 2: Correlation matrix for the TEX-Chlorine (cases 1-3) and the TEX-HEU (cases 4-8) cases using the combined model, experimental, and nuclear data covariances.

The χ^2/ν calculated with only the Σ_{model} and $\Sigma_{\text{experimental}}$ was found to be $\chi^2/\nu=48.792$. The inclusion of $\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$ drop this to $\chi^2/\nu=2.126$. This χ^2 per degree of freedom corresponds to a high p-value of ≈ 0.97 . The observed χ^2 statistic is much smaller than expected under the null hypothesis (i.e., the MCNP model and nuclear data agree well with the experiment). This suggests no evidence to reject the model, but that the nuclear data uncertainties may be overestimated. Without the inclusion of Σ_{model} , i.e. only utilizing $\Sigma_{\text{experimental}}$ and $\Sigma_{\text{Nuclear Data}}$, the total χ^2/ν value was found to be 3.201. This, as expected, is also an overestimation of the χ^2/ν value due to ignoring the experimental correlations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The addition of experimental covariances may have a significant impact on the calculated χ^2 value and shows their importance; omitting them may result in the incorrect conclusion that the disagreement between experiment and code/nuclear data library is more significant that it truly is. Interbenchmark comparisons are provided for the first time through this novel method. The correlation between two similar benchmark evaluations provides insight on the true correlations between such experiments and elucidate the importance of accurately quantifying the total covariances. The inclusion of model and experimental covariance to the performance of similarity metrics, such as q_c , are an interesting prospect for investigation in applications where multiple benchmark evaluations are used to maximize q_c similarity and this topic is the subject of future work.

The covariance determination methods presented here are built upon the already performed uncertainty quantification as part of the ICSBEP benchmarking process. No substantial additional work is needed to fabricate these covariances. The usefulness of these covariances, as well as the potential harm for their neglect, is highlighted by the work presented here. Future work to capture more

benchmark evaluations is underway.

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